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4. Motives of Tourist Attending Special Events: The Case of Kochi Muziris Biennale in Kerala

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Abstract

This paper investigates that motives of tourist attending special events. The study, main focus on special events like Kochi Muziris Biennale. Special events are key motivators for tourism. While there is large number literature regard event tourism motivation, this study discuss on the role of motivations is important to maintain high satisfaction level and to meet tourist demands. The present study investigates whether the present motivation factors are considered in different special events. Consequently, it mainly focused on Kochi Muziris Biennale organised by Kochi Muziris Biennale Foundation incorporation with tourism organisation. The study found that, while there may be difference in the motivations for attending tourist in the special events.

Keywords: Special events, Event Tourism, Event Novelty, Mega Event, Biennale.

Introduction

Event tourism becomes fastest branch of tourism through special events. It represents a major attracting factor for tourist to destination. It is regarded as a unique and frequent, opportunity for host destination to generate large media attractions and visitors. Special interest tourist more attracted and participating in large variety of products and experience offered by event tourism. It provides an opportunity to focus the destination's various heritage, local traditions, ethnic backgrounds, and cultural landscape. In addition, the festival generates a significant amount of business and economic value to the host destinations.

Kerala tourism has been conducting different small and mega-events to promote tourism. Kochi has the rich trading and travellers for centuries from the around world. Souza, R. E. D., & Politics, C. (2014) describes that "The Kochi Muziris Biennale has witnessed social and cultural effects of its rapid economic growth, especially the impact of this growth on contemporary art and visual culture". Today, Kochi Muziris Biennale is the world youngest